

Supporting Information: Advancing Fundamental Understanding of Retention Interactions in Supercritical Fluid Chromatography Using Artificial Neural Networks: Polar Stationary Phases with OH moieties

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S1. Experimental Part

Table S1: List of analytes; their physicochemical properties and elution on tested columns (BEH, silica, diol) using three tested organic modifiers, namely MeOH, MeOH + 10 mM NH₃, and MeOH + 2% H₂O.

Table S2: Molecular descriptors used in the study, calculated with CDK Descriptor Calculator (v.1.4.8).

Table S3: Molecular descriptors used in the study grouped by primary category.

Figure S1. (A) The chemical structure of tested -OH stationary phases, (B) the effect of LSER parameters on silica, BEH, and diol columns, and (C) a spider diagram characterizing stationary phases based on LSER.

S2. Results

Table S4. Molecular descriptors with the highest effect on the retention of compounds identified from the weights assigned by the ANNs after 500 training cycles.

Figure S2. Heatmap of molecular descriptor weights representing their effect on the retention on silica column.

Figure S3. Heatmap of molecular descriptor weights representing their effect on the retention on hybrid silica.

Figure S4. Heatmap of molecular descriptor weights representing their effect on the retention on diol column.

Figure S5. General illustration of molecules with high and low values of RPCG and RHSA.

Figure S6. General illustration of molecules with high and low values of RNCG and RNCS.

Figure S7. Retention times of selected acidic and alkaline compounds on silica, BEH, diol column using MeOH.

Figure S8. (A) Histogram of standard deviations (SD) between weights of molecular descriptors calculated by ANN using the original and extended set of analytes measured on BEH column using MeOH as organic modifier. (B) Comparison of weights of molecular descriptors with the highest SD.

Figure S9. Principal Component Analysis of original set of 52 compounds (blue) and additional compounds eluting on silica and diol column (red).

Figure S10. Retention time of the 5 analytes with the highest values of FMF measured on silica column using MeOH (blue), MeOH+2% H₂O (yellow), and MeOH+10 mmol/L NH₃ (green).

Figure S11. Chemical structure of acebutolol with highlighted -NH- groups.

Figure S12. Percentage of analytes with increased (purple) and decreased (blue) retention times at selected data points when compared to the 1st injection on diol column.

Figure S13. Comparison of weights of the molecular descriptors most affected over time on diol column.

Figure S14. Percentage of analytes with increased (purple) and decreased (blue) retention times at selected data points when compared to the 1st injection on BEH column.

Figure S15. Weights of khs,sNH₂ and MDEO-22 molecular descriptors determined by ANN based on the analyses on BEH column at the 1st injection (0M), after 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, and 12 months (M), and after regeneration (R).

Figure S16. Comparison of retention time shifts over time for alkaline and acidic compounds analyzed on a BEH column using MeOH as organic modifier.

Figure S17. Percentage of analytes with increased (purple) and decreased (blue) retention times at selected data points when compared to the 1st injection on silica column.

Figure S18. Comparison of retention time shifts over time on silica column using (A) methanol, (B) MeOH+10 mmol/L NH₃, and (C) MeOH+ 2% H₂O as organic modifier.

Figure S19. Comparison of weights of the molecular descriptors most affected over time on silica column.

Figure S20. Comparison of % errors calculated between tR after regeneration and tR at the first injection on silica, BEH, and diol columns. %-error less than 0.5% (dark blue), 0.5 - 1.0% (light blue), 1.0 -2.0% (yellow), 2.0 -5.0% (pink), and over 5% (red).

Figure S21: Comparison of changes in retention time and peak width after regeneration procedure. k' closer to the value of the first injection after regeneration (blue) vs. after 12 months (red).

S1. Experimental part

Table S1: List of analytes; their physicochemical properties, including molecular weight (MW), acidic/basic properties (pKa), lipophilicity (logP), number of H acceptors and donors, and molecular formula; and elution on tested columns (BEH, silica, diol) using three tested organic modifiers, namely MeOH, MeOH + 10 mM NH₃, and MeOH + 2% H₂O. n/a means, that analyte did not elute on any of the columns.

n.	CAS No.	analyte	Mw	pKa acid	pKa basic	log P	H acc.	H donor	molecular formula	MeOH	MeOH + 10 mM NH ₄	MeOH + 2% H ₂ O
1	841-67-8	(-)-thalidomide	258.23	10.7	-2.55	0.33	1	7	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
2	2614-06-4	(+)-thalidomide	258.23	10.7	-2.55	0.33	1	7	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
3	303-38-8	2,3-dihydroxy benzoic acid	154.12	2.96	-	1.62	4	3	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	silica	BEH; silica	n/a
4	89-86-1	2,4-dihydroxy benzoic acid	154.12	3.32	-	1.77	4	3	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
5	490-79-9	2,5-dihydroxy benzoic acid	154.12	3.01	-	1.40	4	3	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
6	303-07-1	2,6-dihydroxy benzoic acid	154.12	1.3	-	2.38	4	3	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	n/a	BEH; silica; diol	n/a
7	583-17-5	2-hydroxy cinnamic acid	164.16	4.51	-	1.02	3	2	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
8	362-07-2	2-methoxyestradiol	302.41	10.29	-	3.84	3	2	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₃	BEH; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; diol
9	99-50-3	3,4-dihydroxy benzoic acid	154.12	4.45	-	1.01	4	3	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	silica; diol	n/a	silica; diol
10	99-10-5	3,5-dihydroxy benzoic acid	154.12	3.96	-	0.81	4	3	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	BEH; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
11	530-59-6	4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid	224.21	4.53	-	1.00	5	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
12	588-30-7	3-hydroxy cinnamic acid	164.16	4.38	-	0.93	3	2	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
13	537-73-5	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxycinnamic acid	194.18	4.53	-	0.79	4	2	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄	BEH; diol	BEH; diol	BEH; silica; diol
14	530-57-4	4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybenzoic acid	198.17	4.33	-	1.28	5	2	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
15	121-34-6	4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoic acid	168.15	4.45	-	1.30	4	2	C ₈ H ₈ O ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
16	99-96-7	4-hydroxybenzoic acid	138.12	4.57	-	1.40	3	2	C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
17	100-09-4	4-methoxy benzoic acid	152.15	4.47	-	1.78	3	1	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
18	154229-18-2	abiraterone acetate	391.55	5.31	-	6.58	3	0	C ₂₆ H ₃₃ NO ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
19	37517-30-9	acebutolol	336.43	13.78	9.4	1.77	6	3	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₄	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol

n.	CAS No.	analyte	Mw	pKa acid	pKa basic	log P	H acc.	H donor	molecular formula	MeOH	MeOH + 10 mM NH ₄	MeOH + 2% H ₂ O
20	138112-76-2	agomelatine	243.3	16.17	-0.53	2.47	3	1	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
21	52-39-1	aldosterone	360.44	12.98	-	0.70	2	7	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
22	59-02-9	alpha-tocopherol	430.71	11.4	-	10.96	2	1	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
23	1721-51-3	alpha-tocotrienol	424.66	11.4	-	9.70	2	1	C ₂₉ H ₄₄ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
24	520-36-5	apigenin	270.24	6.53	-	2.13	5	3	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
25	29122-68-7	atenolol	266.34	13.88	9.43	0.36	5	4	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
26	98-55-5	a-terpinol	154.25	14.94	-	2.54	1	2	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
27	83015-26-3	atomoxetine	255.35	10.15	-	3.36	2	1	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
28	134523-00-5	atorvastatin	558.64	4.29	0.38	3.85	7	4	C ₃₃ H ₃₅ FN ₂ O ₅	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
29	148-03-8	beta tocopherol	416.68	11.05	-	10.72	2	1	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O ₂	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
30	490-23-3	beta tocotrienol	410.63	11.05	-	9.46	2	1	C ₂₈ H ₄₂ O ₂	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
31	378-44-9	betamethasone	392.46	12.13	-	2.03	5	3	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ FO ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
32	62658-63-3	bopindolol	380.48	17.59	9.4	4.82	5	2	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
33	51-20-7	bromo uracil	190.98	6.77	-	-0.21	4	2	C ₄ H ₃ BrN ₂ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
34	58-08-2	caffein	194.19	0.52	-	-0.63	6	0	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
35	154-23-4	catechin	290.27	9.54	-	0.61	5	11	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
36	83881-51-0	cetirizin	388.89	3.46	6.71	1.62	5	1	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₃	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
37	50-22-6	cortikosterone	346.46	12.98	-	1.95	2	6	C ₂₁ H ₃₀ O ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
38	71-30-7	cytosine	111.1	9	4.18	-1.96	4	3	C ₄ H ₅ N ₃ O	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
39	1009119-64-5	daclatasvir	738.88	10.92	6.56	2.51	14	4	C ₄₀ H ₅₀ N ₈ O ₆	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
40	133099-04-4	darifenacin	426.55	15.7	9.32	3.78	4	2	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
41	302962-49-8	dasatinib	488.01	10.94	7.29	0.14	9	3	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ ClN ₇ O ₂ S	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol

n.	CAS No.	analyte	Mw	pKa acid	pKa basic	log P	H acc.	H donor	molecular formula	MeOH	MeOH + 10 mM NH ₄	MeOH + 2% H ₂ O
42	53-43-0	dehydro-epi-androsterone	288.43	15.02	-	3.31	1	3	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
43	119-13-1	delta tocopherol	402.65	10.7	-	10.49	2	1	C ₂₇ H ₄₆ O ₂	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
44	25612-59-3	delta tocotrienol	396.61	10.69	-	9.23	2	1	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
45	50-47-5	desipramin	266.38	-	10.4	3.97	2	1	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
46	50-02-2	dexamethasone	392.46	12.13	-	2.03	5	3	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ FO ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
47	915087-33-1	enzalutamide	464.44	13.88	-1.99	2.98	6	1	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ F ₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
48	57-91-0	estradiol	272.38	10.27	-	4.15	2	2	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
49	4245-41-4	estradiol acetate	314.42	15.06	-	4.46	3	1	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
50	50-27-1	estriol	288.38	10.25	-	2.53	3	3	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
51	53-16-7	estron	270.37	10.25	-	3.62	2	1	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
52	774-40-3	(±)-ethyl mandelate	194.23	12.31	-	1.76	3	1	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
53	470-82-6	eucalyptol (1,8-cineole)	154.25	-	-4.2	2.80	0	1	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	n/a	n/a	n/a
54	163222-33-1	ezetimibe	409.43	9.72	-0.2	3.96	4	2	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ F ₂ NO ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
55	4602-84-0	farnesol	222.37	14.69	-	4.83	1	1	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
56	29679-58-1	fenoprofen	242.27	4.2	-	3.72	3	1	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
57	5104-49-4	flurbiprofen	244.26	4.14	-	3.66	2	1	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FO ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
58	93957-54-1	fluvastatin	411.47	4.27	-	4.57	5	3	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ FNO ₄	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
59	54-28-4	gamma-tocopherol	416.68	11.05	-	10.72	2	1	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O ₂	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
60	14101-61-2	gamma-tocotrienol	410.63	11.05	-	9.46	2	1	C ₂₈ H ₄₂ O ₂	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
61	520-33-2	hesperetin	302.28	7.49	-	1.94	6	3	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₆	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
62	520-26-3	hesperidin	610.56	7.15	-	-1.21	15	8	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₅	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
63	4270-27-3	chlorouracil (4-Chloro-2,6-dihydroxypyrimidine)	146.53	6.24	-	0.03	4	2	C ₄ H ₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
64	15687-27-1	ibuprofen	206.28	4.41	-	3.50	2	1	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol

n.	CAS No.	analyte	Mw	pKa acid	pKa basic	log P	H acc.	H donor	molecular formula	MeOH	MeOH + 10 mM NH ₄	MeOH + 2% H ₂ O
65	50-49-7	imipramine	280.41	-	9.49	4.36	2	0	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
66	1516864-05-3	atorvastatin impurity A	540.65	4.29	0.39	3.91	7	4	C ₃₃ H ₃₆ N ₂ O ₅	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
67	842103-12-2	atorvastatin impurity B	558.64	4.29	0.38	3.85	7	4	C ₃₃ H ₃₅ FN ₂ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
68	693793-53-2	atorvastatin impurity C	576.63	4.29	0.37	3.78	7	4	C ₃₃ H ₃₄ F ₂ N ₂ O ₅	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
69	53-86-1	indomethacin	357.79	3.96	-	4.25	5	1	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ClNO ₄	BEH; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
70	480-19-3	isorhamnetine	316.26	6.31	-	2.79	4	11	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	n/a	diol	n/a
71	22071-15-4	ketoprofen	254.28	4.23	-	2.91	3	1	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
72	36894-69-6	labetalol	328.41	8.21	9.3	2.72	5	5	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
73	125995-03-1	atorvastatin lactone	540.62	13.39	0.38	3.90	6	2	C ₃₃ H ₃₃ FN ₂ O ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
74	1256388-51-8	ledipasvir	889	11.2	5.42	4.54	14	4	C ₄₉ H ₅₄ F ₂ N ₈ O ₆	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
75	75330-75-5	lovastatin	404.54	13.49	-	4.31	5	1	C ₂₄ H ₃₆ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
76	491-70-3	luteolin	286.24	6.5	-	2.70	6	4	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	silica	n/a	silica
77	376348-65-1	maraviroc	513.67	14.8	10.24	5.30	6	1	C ₂₉ H ₄₁ F ₂ N ₅ O	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
78	51384-51-1	metoprolol	267.36	13.89	9.43	1.63	4	2	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ NO ₃	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
79	480-41-1	naringenin	272.25	7.52	-	2.63	3	8	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
80	10236-47-2	naringin	580.54	7.17	-	-0.20	8	22	C ₂₇ H ₃₂ O ₁₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
81	99-87-6	p-cymene	134.22	14	-	4.01	0	0	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	n/a	n/a	n/a
82	60-81-1	phloridzine	436.41	7.15	-	-0.37	7	17	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₁₀	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
83	13523-86-9	pindolol	248.32	13.94	9.54	1.68	4	3	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
84	147511-69-1	pitavastatin	421.46	4.24	4.68	1.92	3	8	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ FNO ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
85	81093-37-0	pravastatin	424.53	4.31	-	2.21	4	11	C ₂₃ H ₃₆ O ₇	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol

n.	CAS No.	analyte	Mw	pKa acid	pKa basic	log P	H acc.	H donor	molecular formula	MeOH	MeOH + 10 mM NH ₄	MeOH + 2% H ₂ O
86	525-66-6	propranolol	259.34	13.84	9.5	2.90	2	5	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ NO ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
87	501-36-0	resveratrol	228.24	9.22	-	3.02	3	3	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
88	155213-67-5	ritonavir	720.94	11.47	2.51	2.33	11	4	C ₃₇ H ₄₈ N ₆ O ₅ S ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
89	123441-03-2	S-rivastigmine	250.34	-	8.62	2.06	0	4	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
90	415973-05-6	R-rivastigmine	250.34	-	8.62	2.06	0	4	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
91	18559-94-9	salbutamol	239.31	9.99	9.62	0.69	4	8	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ NO ₃	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
92	92-61-5	scopoletin	192.17	7.91	-	1.38	4	1	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
93	138-59-0	shikimic acid	174.15	4.48	-	-2.22	5	4	C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
94	923604-59-5	simeprevir	749.94	4.47	3.01	6.10	12	2	C ₃₈ H ₄₇ N ₅ O ₇ S ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
95	79902-63-9	simvastatin	418.57	13.49	-	4.72	5	1	C ₂₅ H ₃₈ O ₅	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
96	486460-32-6	sitagliptin	407.31	-	7.2	2.06	6	2	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ F ₆ N ₅ O	silica	BEH; silica	silica
97	1190307-88-0	sofosbuvir	529.45	9.39	-3.26	2.21	12	3	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ FN ₃ O ₉ P	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
98	603-61-2	tamarixetin	316.26	6.31	-	2.67	7	4	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	silica	silica; diol	silica; diol
99	611-40-5	tectoridin	464.4	6.1	-	0.54	11	6	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁	silica; diol	silica; diol	silica; diol
100	548-77-6	tectorigenin	300.26	6.49	-	2.84	3	9	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	silica; diol
101	58-22-0	testosterone	288.43	15.06	-	3.18	1	3	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
102	274693-27-5	ticagrelor	522.57	13.26	3.05	2.02	4	14	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ F ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
103	140-10-3	trans-cinnamic acid	148.16	4.34	-	1.21	2	1	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
104	501-94-0	tyrosol	138.16	10.17	-	0.85	2	2	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
105	66-22-8	uracil	112.09	8.95	-4.19	-1.04	4	2	C ₄ H ₄ N ₂ O ₂	silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
106	121-33-5	vanillin	152.15	7.78	-	1.21	3	1	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol
107	224785-90-4	vardeafil	488.6	9.86	7.15	3.64	10	1	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ S	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol	BEH; silica; diol

Table S2: Molecular descriptors used in the study, calculated with CDK Descriptor Calculator (v.1.4.8).

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
ALOGP <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i> (atom additive logP and molar refractivity values; described by Ghose and Crippen)	ALogP	Ghose-Crippen LogKow (octanol-water coefficient)
	AlogP2	Ghose-Crippen octanol water coefficient squared
	AMR	Ghose-Crippen molar refractivity
APol <i>Electronic Descriptor</i>	Apol	sum of the atomic polarizabilities (including implicit hydrogens)
AcidicGroupContent <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	nAcid	number of acidic groups
BCUT <i>Hybrid Descriptor</i> (eigenvalue-based descriptor noted for its utility in chemical diversity described by Pearlman et al; a weighted version of the Burden matrix)	BCUTw-1l	nhigh (number of highest eigenvalue) lowest atom weighted BCUTS
	BCUTw-1h	nlow (number of lowest eigenvalue) highest atom weighted BCUTS
	BCUTc-1l	nhigh (number of highest eigenvalue) lowest partial charge weighted BCUTS
	BCUTc-1h	nlow (number of lowest eigenvalue) highest partial charge weighted BCUTS
	BCUTp-1l	nhigh (number of highest eigenvalue) lowest polarizability weighted BCUTS
	BCUTp-1h	nlow (number of lowest eigenvalue) highest polarizability weighted BCUTS
	PPSA-1	partial positive surface area; sum of surface area on positive parts of molecule
	PPSA-2	partial positive surface area * total positive charge on the molecule
	PPSA-3	charge weighted partial positive surface area
	PNSA-1	partial negative surface area; sum of surface area on negative parts of molecule
PNSA-2	partial negative surface area * total negative charge on the molecule	
PNSA-3	charge weighted partial negative surface area	
DPSA-1	difference of PPSA-1 and PNSA-1	
DPSA-2	difference of PPSA-2 and PNSA-2	
DPSA-3	difference of PPSA-3 and PNSA-3	
FPSA-1	PPSA-1 / total molecular surface area	
FPSA-2	PPSA-2 / total molecular surface area	
FPSA-3	PPSA-3 / total molecular surface area	
FPNA-1	PNSA-1 / total molecular surface area	
FPNA-2	PNSA-2 / total molecular surface area	
FPNA-3	PNSA-3 / total molecular surface area	
WPSA-1	PPSA-1 * total molecular surface area / 1000	
WPSA-2	PPSA-2 * total molecular surface area / 1000	
WPSA-3	PPSA-3 * total molecular surface area / 1000	
WPNA-1	PNSA-1 * total molecular surface area / 1000	
WPNA-2	PNSA-2 * total molecular surface area / 1000	
WPNA-3	PNSA-3 * total molecular surface area / 1000	
RPCG	relative positive charge; most positive charge / total positive charge	
RNCG	relative negative charge; most negative charge / total negative charge	
RPCS	relative positive charge surface area; most positive surface area * RPCG	
CPSA <i>Electronic and Geometrical Descriptor</i> (29 Charged Partial Surface Area Descriptors)		

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
	RNCS	relative negative charge surface area; most negative surface area * RNCG
	THSA	sum of solvent accessible surface areas of atoms with absolute value of partial charges less than 0.2
	TPSA	sum of solvent accessible surface areas of atoms with absolute value of partial charges less than 0.2
	RHSA	THSA / total molecular surface area
	RPSA	TPSA / total molecular surface area
WHIM <i>Hybrid Descriptor</i> <i>(Weighted Holistic Invariant Molecular descriptors; based on a number of atom weightings)</i>	Wlambda1.unity;	directional descriptor; related to molecular size
	Wlambda2.unity	directional descriptor; related to molecular size
	Wlambda3.unity	directional descriptor; related to molecular size
	Wnu1.unity	directional descriptor; related to molecular shape
	Wnu2.unity	directional descriptor; related to molecular shape
	Weta1.unity	directional descriptor; related to density of the atoms distribution
	Weta2.unity	directional descriptor; related to density of the atoms distribution
	Weta3.unity	directional descriptor; related to density of the atoms distribution
	WT.unity	non-directional descriptor; related to linear contributions to the total molecular dimension
	WA.unity	non-directional descriptor; related to quadratic contributions to the total molecular dimension
	WV.unity	non-directional descriptor; contains also the third-order term;
	WK.unity	non-directional descriptor; molecular shape
	WD.unity	non-directional descriptor; the total molecular density
MDE <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(Molecular Distance Edge Descriptors for C, O, and N)</i>	MDEC-11	molecular distance edge between all primary carbons
	MDEC-12	molecular distance edge between all primary and secondary carbons
	MDEC-13	molecular distance edge between all primary and tertiary carbons
	MDEC-14	molecular distance edge between all primary and quaternary carbons
	MDEC-22	molecular distance edge between all secondary carbons
	MDEC-23	molecular distance edge between all secondary and tertiary carbons
	MDEC-24	molecular distance edge between all secondary and quaternary carbons
	MDEC-33	molecular distance edge between all tertiary carbons
	MDEC-34	molecular distance edge between all tertiary and quaternary carbons
	MDEC-44	molecular distance edge between all quaternary carbons
	MDEO-11	molecular distance edge between all primary oxygens
	MDEO-12	molecular distance edge between all primary and secondary oxygens
	MDEO-22	molecular distance edge between all secondary oxygens
	MDEN-12	molecular distance edge between all primary and secondary nitrogens
	MDEN-13	molecular distance edge between all primary and tertiary nitrogens
MDEN-22	molecular distance edge between all secondary nitrogens	
MDEN-23	molecular distance edge between all secondary and tertiary nitrogens	
MDEN-33	molecular distance edge between all tertiary nitrogens	
AromaticAtomsCount	naAromAtom	number of aromatic atoms in an atom container

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
Constitutional Descriptor AromaticBondsCount <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	nAromBond	number of aromatic atoms in an AtomContainer; based on the number of aromatic bounds
AtomCount <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	nAtom	number of atoms of a certain element type
AutocorrelationCharge <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(the Moreau-Broto autocorrelation descriptors using partial charges)</i>	ATSc1 ATSc2 ATSc3 ATSc4 ATSc5	ATS autocorrelation descriptor, weighted by charges ATS autocorrelation descriptor, weighted by charges
AutocorrelationMass <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(the Moreau-Broto autocorrelation descriptors using atomic weight)</i>	ATSm1 ATSm2 ATSm3 ATSm4 ATSm5	ATS autocorrelation descriptor, weighted by scaled atomic mass ATS autocorrelation descriptor, weighted by scaled atomic mass
AutocorrelationPolarizability <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(the Moreau-Broto autocorrelation descriptors using polarizability)</i>	ATSp1 ATSp2 ATSp3 ATSp4 ATSp5	ATS autocorrelation descriptor, weighted by polarizability ATS autocorrelation descriptor, weighted by polarizability
BPol <i>Electronic Descriptor</i>	bpol	sum of the absolute value of the difference between atomic polarizabilities of all bonded atoms in the molecule (including implicit hydrogens)
BasicGroupCount <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	nBase	number of basic groups
BondCount <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	nBx	single value with name nBX where X can be s(single bond), d (double), t (triple), a (aromatic), ""(all)
CarbonTypes <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(carbon connectivity in the terms of hybridization)</i>	C1SP1 C1SP2 C2SP2 C3SP2 C1SP3 C2SP3 C3SP3 C4SP3	triple bound carbon bound to one other carbon triple bound carbon bound to two other carbons doubly bound carbon bound to two other carbons doubly bound carbon bound to three other carbons singly bound carbon bound to one other carbon singly bound carbon bound to two other carbons singly bound carbon bound to three other carbons singly bound carbon bound to four other carbons
ChiChain <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(evaluates the Kier & Hall Chi chain indices of orders 3,4,5 and 6; type of chain)</i>	SCH-3 SCH-4 SCH-5 SCH-6 SCH-7 VCH-3	simple chain, order 3 simple chain, order 4 simple chain, order 5 simple chain, order 6 simple chain, order 7 valence chain, order 3

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
	VCH-4	valence chain, order 4
	VCH-5	valence chain, order 5
	VCH-6	valence chain, order 6
	VCH-7	valence chain, order 7
ChiCluster <i>Topological Descriptor</i> (evaluates the Kier & Hall Chi cluster indices of orders 3,4,5, and 6)	SC-3	simple cluster, order 3
	SC-4	simple cluster, order 4
	SC-5	simple cluster, order 5
	SC-6	simple cluster, order 6
	VC-3	valence cluster, order 3
	VC-4	valence cluster, order 4
	VC-5	valence cluster, order 5
	VC-6	valence cluster, order 6
ChiPathCluster <i>Topological Descriptor</i> (evaluates the Kier & Hall Chi path cluster indices of orders 4,5, and 6)	SPC-4	simple path cluster, order 4
	SPC-5	simple path cluster, order 5
	SPC-6	simple path cluster, order 6
	VPC-4	valence path cluster, order 4
	VPC-5	valence path cluster, order 5
	VPC-6	valence path cluster, order 6
ChiPath <i>Topological Descriptor</i> (evaluates the Kier & Hall Chi path indices of orders 0,1,2,3,4,5,6 and 7)	SP-0	simple path, order 0
	SP-1	simple path, order 1
	SP-2	simple path, order 2
	SP-3	simple path, order 3
	SP-4	simple path, order 4
	SP-5	simple path, order 5
	SP-6	simple path, order 6
	SP-7	simple path, order 7
	VP-0	valence path, order 0
	VP-1	valence path, order 1
	VP-2	valence path, order 2
	VP-3	valence path, order 3
	VP-4	valence path, order 4
	VP-5	valence path, order 5
VP-6	valence path, order 6	
VP-7	valence path, order 7	
EccentricConnectivityIndex <i>Topological Descriptor</i>	ECCEN	combining distance and adjacency information
FMF <i>Topological Descriptor</i>	FMF	ratio of heavy atoms in the framework to the total number of heavy atoms in the molecule; characterize the complexity of the molecule
FragmentComplexity <i>Topological Descriptor</i>	fragC	Complexity of a system; $C = \frac{\text{abs}(B^2 - A^2 + A) + H}{100}$ where C=complexity, A=number of non-hydrogen atoms, B=number of bonds and H=number of heteroatoms

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
GravitationalIndex <i>Geometrical Descriptor</i> <i>(mass distribution of the molecule)</i>	GRAV-1	gravitational index of heavy atoms
	GRAV-2	square root of gravitational index of heavy atoms
	GRAV-3	cube root of gravitational index of heavy atoms
	GRAVH-1	gravitational index - hydrogens included
	GRAVH-2	square root of hydrogen-included gravitational index
	GRAVH-3	cube root of hydrogen-included gravitational index
	GRAV-4	grav1 for all pairs of atoms (not just bonded pairs)
HBondAcceptorCount <i>Electronic Descriptor</i>	GRAV-5	grav2 for all pairs of atoms (not just bonded pairs)
	GRAV-6	grav3 for all pairs of atoms (not just bonded pairs)
HBondDonorCount <i>Electronic Descriptor</i>	nHBAcc	the number of H bond acceptors using a slightly simplified version of the PHACIR atom types. The groups counted as acceptors: (i) Any O where the formal charge of the oxygen is non-positive (i.e. formal charge ≤ 0) except an aromatic ether O and an O that is adjacent to a N; (ii) Any N where the formal charge of the N is non-positive (i.e. formal charge ≤ 0) except a N that is adjacent to an O
	nHBDon	number of H bond donors using a slightly simplified version of the PHACIR atom types. The groups counted as donors: (i) Any-OH where the formal charge of the O is non-negative (i.e. formal charge ≥ 0); (ii) Any-NH where the formal charge of the N is non-negative (i.e. formal charge ≥ 0)
HybridizationRatio <i>Topological Descriptor</i>	HybRatio	the fraction of sp ³ carbons to sp ² carbons; complexity of the molecule
KierHallSmarts <i>Topological Descriptor</i> <i>(it counts the number of occurrences of the E-state fragments; - single bond; =double bond; # triple bond; : aromatic bond)</i>	khs.sCH3	count of atom-type E-state: -CH ₃
	khs.ssCH2	count of atom-type E-state: -CH ₂ -
	khs.dsCH	count of atom-type E-state: =CH-
	khs.aaCH	count of atom-type E-state: :CH:
	khs.sssCH	count of atom-type E-state: >CH-
	khs.tsC	count of atom-type E-state: #C-
	khs.dssC	count of atom-type E-state: =C<
	khs.aasC	count of atom-type E-state: :C:-
	khs.aaaC	count of atom-type E-state: ::C:
	khs.ssssC	count of atom-type E-state: >C<
	khs.sNH2	count of atom-type E-state: -NH ₂
	khs.ssNH	count of atom-type E-state: -NH ₂ ⁺
	khs.aaN	count of atom-type E-state: :NH:
	khs.tN	count of atom-type E-state: #N
	khs.aaN	count of atom-type E-state: :N:
	khs.sssN	count of atom-type E-state: >N-
khs.aasN	count of atom-type E-state: :N:-	
khs.sOH	count of atom-type E-state: -OH	
khs.dO	count of atom-type E-state: =O	

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
	khs.ssO	count of atom-type E-state: -O-
	khs.aaO	count of atom-type E-state: :O:
	khs.sF	count of atom-type E-state: -F
	khs.dsssP	count of atom-type E-state: ->P=
	khs.dS	count of atom-type E-state: =S
	khs.ssS	count of atom-type E-state: -S-
	khs.aaS	count of atom-type E-state: :S:
	khs.ddssS	count of atom-type E-state: >S==
	khs.sCl	count of atom-type E-state: -Cl
	khs.sBr	count of atom-type E-state: -Br
KappaShapeIndices	Kier1	first kappa shape index
<i>Topological Descriptor</i>	Kier2	second kappa shape index
<i>(Kier and Hall kappa molecular shape indices compare the molecular graph with minimal and maximal molecular graphs)</i>	Kier3	third kappa shape index
MomentOfInertia	MOMI-X	moment of inertia along X axis
<i>Geometrical Descriptor</i>	MOMI-Y	moment of inertia along Y axis
<i>(principal moment of inertia, their ratios, and radius of gyration; characterize the mass distribution of a molecule)</i>	MOMI-Z	moment of inertia along Z axis
	MOMI-XY	ratio X/Y
	MOMI-XZ	ratio X/Z
	MOMI-YZ	ratio Y/Z
	MOMI-R	radius of the gyration of the molecule
WeightedPath	WTPT-1	molecular ID
<i>Topological Descriptor</i>	WTPT-2	molecular ID / number of atoms
<i>(The weighted path (molecular ID) descriptors described by Randic. They characterize molecular branching.)</i>	WTPT-3	sum of path lengths starting from heteroatoms
	WTPT-4	sum of path lengths starting from oxygens
	WTPT-5	sum of path lengths starting from nitrogens
WienerNumbers	WPATH	weiner path number
<i>Topological Descriptor</i>	WPOL	weiner polarity number
<i>(described by Randic, characterize molecular branching)</i>		
LargestChain	nAtomLC	number of atoms in the largest chain
<i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>		
LargestPiSystem	nAtomP	number of atoms in the largest pi system
<i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>		
LongestAliphaticChain	nAtomLAC	number of atoms in the longest aliphatic chain
<i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>		
PetitjeanNumber	PetitjeanNuber	the eccentricity of a vertex corresponds to the distance from that vertex to the most remote vertex in the graph. The distance is obtained from the distance matrix as the count of edges between the two vertices. If r(i) is the largest matrix entry in row i of the distance
<i>Topological Descriptor</i>		

type and class of molecular descriptors	individual descriptors (abbreviation)	meaning
		matrix D, then the radius is defined as the smallest of the r(i). The graph diameter D is defined as the largest vertex eccentricity in the graph
MannholdLogP <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	MLogP	prediction of logP based on the number of carbon and hetero atoms
PetitjeanShapeIndex <i>Topological/Geometrical Descriptor (anisotropy of molecule)</i>	topoShape	topological shape index
	geomShape	geometric shape index
RuleOfFive <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	LipinskiFailures	number failures of the Lipinski's Rule Of 5
TPSA <i>Topological/Electronic Descriptor</i>	TopoPSA	topological polar surface area based on fragment contributions
VABC <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	VABC	values derived from the van der Waals Volume as a Sum of Atomic and Bond Contributions (VABC)
VAdjMa <i>Topological Descriptor</i>	VAdjMat	Vertex adjacency information (magnitude): $1 + \log_2 m$ where m is the number of heavy-atom bonds
Weight <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	MW	based on the weight of atoms of a certain element type
XLogP <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	XLogP	prediction of logP based on the atom-type method
ZagrebIndex <i>Topological Descriptor</i>	Zagreb	the sum of the squares of atom degree over all heavy atoms i
RotatableBondsCount <i>Constitutional Descriptor</i>	nRotB	number of rotatable bonds is given by the SMARTS specified by Daylight
Other Constitutional Descriptors	tpsaEfficiency	Polar surface area expressed as a ratio to molecular size
	nSmallRings	Number of small rings from size 3 to 9
	nAromRings	Number of aromatic rings
	nRingBlocks	Total number of distinct ring blocks
	nAromBlocks	Total number of "aromatically connected components"
	nRings3	individual breakdown of small ring, size 3
	nRings4	individual breakdown of small ring, size 4
	nRings5	individual breakdown of small ring, size 5
nRings6	individual breakdown of small ring, size 6	
nRings7	individual breakdown of small ring, size 7	

Table S3: Molecular descriptors used in the study grouped by primary category. For the description of molecular descriptors see SI Table S2.

category	molecular descriptor
lipophilicity	AlogP AlogP2 MLogP XLogP
spectral	AMR
polarizability	Apol BCUTp-1l BCUTp-1h ATSp1 ATSp2 ATSp3 ATSp4 ATSp5 bpol
physicochemical properties	nAcid nBase nHBAcc nHBDon LipinskiFailures VABC
size/mass	MW BCUTw-1l BCUTw-1h Wlambda1.unity; Wlambda2.unity Wlambda3.unity ATSm1 ATSm2 ATSm3 ATSm4 ATSm5 GRAV-1 GRAV-2 GRAV-3 GRAVH-1 GRAVH-2 GRAVH-3 GRAV-4 GRAV-5 GRAV-6
charge/surface area	BCUTc-1l BCUTc-1h PPSA-1 PPSA-2 PPSA-3 PNSA-1 PNSA-2 PNSA-3 DPSA-1 DPSA-2 DPSA-3 FPSA-1 FPSA-2 FPSA-3 FPNA-1 FPNA-2 FPNA-3

	WPSA-1
	WPSA-2
	WPSA-3
	WPNA-1
	WPNA-2
	WPNA-3
	RPCG
	RNCG
	RPCS
	RNCS
	THSA
	TPSA
	RHSA
	RPSA
	ATSc1
	ATSc2
	ATSc3
	ATSc4
	ATSc5
	TopoPSA
	tpsaEfficiency
shape	Wnu1.unity
	Wnu2.unity
	WT.unity
	WA.unity
	WV.unity
	WK.unity
	Kier1
	Kier2
	Kier3
	MOMI-X
	MOMI-Y
	MOMI-Z
	MOMI-XY
	MOMI-XZ
	MOMI-YZ
	MOMI-R
	FMF
	PetitjeanNuber
	topoShape
	geomShape
	Zagreb
atom distribution/connectivity	Weta1.unity
	Weta2.unity
	Weta3.unity
	WD.unity
	ECCEN
	VAdjMat
	nBx
	nRotB
	khs.sF
	khs.dsssP
	khs.dS
	khs.ssS
	khs.aaS
	khs.ddssS
	khs.sCl
	khs.sBr
	nAtomLC
	nAtomP

	nAtomLAC	
atom distribution/connectivity - carbon	MDEC-11	
	MDEC-12	
	MDEC-13	
	MDEC-14	
	MDEC-22	
	MDEC-23	
	MDEC-24	
	MDEC-33	
	MDEC-34	
	MDEC-44	
	C1SP1	
	C1SP2	
	C2SP2	
	C3SP2	
	C1SP3	
	C2SP3	
	C3SP3	
	C4SP3	
	fragC	
	HybRatio	
	khs.sCH3	
	khs.ssCH2	
	khs.dsCH	
	khs.ssssC	
	khs.sssCH	
	khs.tsC	
	khs.dssC	
	atom distribution/connectivity - oxygen	MDEO-11
		MDEO-12
		MDEO-22
		khs.sOH
khs.dO		
khs.ssO		
atom distribution/connectivity - nitrogen	MDEN-12	
	MDEN-13	
	MDEN-22	
	MDEN-23	
	MDEN-33	
	khs.sNH2	
	khs.ssNH	
	khs.tN	
khs.sssN		
atom distribution/connectivity - aromatic	naAromAtom	
	nAromBond	
	nAtom	
	nSmallRings	
	nAromRings	
	nRingBlocks	
	nAromBlocks	
	nRings3	
	nRings4	
	nRings5	
	nRings6	
	nRings7	
	khs.aaCH	
	khs.aasC	
	khs.aaaC	
khs.aaO		
khs.aaNH		

	khs.aaN khs.aasN
molecular branching	WTPT-1 WTPT-2 WTPT-3 WTPT-4 WTPT-5 WPATH WPOL
topological descriptors of valence electrons, Chi chains, Chi paths	SCH-3 SCH-4 SCH-5 SCH-6 SCH-7 VCH-3 VCH-4 VCH-5 VCH-6 VCH-7 SC-3 SC-4 SC-5 SC-6 VC-3 VC-4 VC-5 VC-6 SPC-4 SPC-5 SPC-6 VPC-4 VPC-5 VPC-6 SP-0 SP-1 SP-2 SP-3 SP-4 SP-5 SP-6 SP-7 VP-0 VP-1 VP-2 VP-3 VP-4 VP-5 VP-6 VP-7

Figure S1. (A) The chemical structure of tested -OH stationary phases, (B) the effect of LSER parameters on silica, BEH, and diol columns, and (C) a spider diagram characterizing stationary phases based on LSER characteristics. Black circles mark columns used for comparison in (B). The values of LSER parameters were taken from the article published by West et al.¹ The spider diagram was reprinted with permission from ref. 2.²

S2. Results

Table S4. Molecular descriptors with the highest effect on the retention using narrowed (52 compounds) and extended sets (57/94/98 compounds) of compounds identified from the weights assigned by the ANNs after 500 training cycles.

	BEH 52 analytes	BEH - extended 57 analytes	silica 52 analytes	silica - extended 94 analytes	diol 52 analytes	diol - extended 98 analytes
descriptors decreasing the retention	BCUTc-1l	<i>BCUTc-1l</i>	nHBAcc	<i>nHBAcc</i>	HybRatio	<i>HybRatio</i>
	MDEO-11	<i>MDEO-11</i>	RHSA	<i>FPSA-3</i>	BCUTc-1l	<i>BCUTp-1l</i>
	XLogP	<i>XLogP</i>	khs.ddssS	<i>khs.ssS</i>	SC-4	<i>SC-4</i>
	khs.dO	<i>khs.ssO</i>	MDEO-11	<i>MDEC-12</i>	RPCG	<i>VC-6</i>
	BCUTc-1h	<i>BCUTp-1l</i>	RPCG	<i>BCUTp-1l</i>	BCUTp-1l	<i>VC-5</i>
	RPCG	<i>nHBAcc</i>	BCUTc-1l	<i>VC-6</i>	BCUTc-1h	<i>VP-6</i>
	RHSA	<i>FNSA-1</i>	BCUTc-1h	<i>VC-5</i>	LipinskiFailures	<i>XLogP</i>
	Khs.ddssS	<i>VC-4</i>	Weta2.unity	<i>VPC-6</i>	khs.dO	<i>nHBAcc</i>
	Weta2.unity	<i>nAtomLC</i>	LipinskiFailures	<i>C1SP3</i>	topoShape	<i>nRingBlocks</i>
	LipinskiFailures	<i>MDEC-12</i>	XLogP	<i>nAromRings</i>	PetitjeanNumber	<i>ATSc1</i>
descriptors increasing the retention	MDEO-22	<i>MDEO-22</i>	tpsaEfficiency	<i>tpsaEfficiency</i>	MDEO-22	<i>MDEO-22</i>
	TPSA	<i>TPSA</i>	MDEO-22	<i>MDEO-22</i>	RNCS	<i>FNSA-2</i>
	nHBDon	<i>nHBDon</i>	nBase	<i>nBase</i>	FMF	<i>TPSA</i>
	khs.aaNH	<i>khs.aaNH</i>	khs.sNH2	<i>khs.aaN</i>	MDEC-13	<i>MDEC-14</i>
	geomShape	<i>geomShape</i>	MDEN-13	<i>MDEC-13</i>	MOMI-XZ	<i>MDEN-12</i>
	MDEC-13	<i>MDEC-23</i>	MDEC-24	<i>MDEC-23</i>	MOMI-YZ	<i>MDEC-34</i>
	RNCS	<i>FNSA-3</i>	Weta3.unity	<i>MDEC-14</i>	khs.aaNH	<i>BCUTp-1h</i>
	FMF	<i>C3SP3</i>	RNCS	<i>MDEO-12</i>	geomShape	<i>Wlambda1.unity</i>
	nRings7	<i>C1SP3</i>	ATSc3	<i>SC-6</i>	C4SP3	<i>Wlambda2.unity</i>
	nAcid	<i>khs.ssNH</i>	RPSA	<i>C4SP3</i>	nAcid	<i>nBase</i>

parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
AlogP																								
Alogp2																								
AMR																								
BCUTw-1l																								
BCUTw-1h																								
BCUTc-1l																								
BCUTc-1h																								
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PPSA-1																								
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RPCS																								
RNCS																								
THSA																								
TPSA																								
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ATSc4																								
ATSc5																								
ATSm1																								
ATSm2																								

parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
ATSm3																								
ATSm4																								
ATSm5																								
ATSp1																								
ATSp2																								
ATSp3																								
ATSp4																								
ATSp5																								
nBase																								
nB																								
bpol																								
C1SP1																								
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C2SP2																								
C3SP2																								
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SCH-7																								
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parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
GRAVH-1																								
GRAVH-2																								
GRAVH-3																								
GRAV-4																								
GRAV-5																								
GRAV-6																								
nHBDon																								
nHBAcc																								
HybRatio																								
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khs,dssC																								
khs,aasC																								
khs,aaaC																								
khs,ssssC																								
khs,sNH2																								
khs,ssNH																								
khs,aaNH																								
khs,tN																								
khs,aaN																								
khs,sssN																								
khs,aasN																								
khs,sOH																								
khs,dO																								
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Figure S2. Heatmap of molecular descriptor weights representing their effect on the retention on silica column determined by ANN. Blue – decreasing retention, red – increasing retention. M – MeOH as organic modifier, N – MeOH+10 mmol/L NH₃ as organic modifier, W- MeOH+2% H₂O as organic modifier.

parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-1st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
ALogP																								
ALogp2																								
AMR																								
BCUTw-1l																								
BCUTw-1h																								
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parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-1st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
ATSm4																								
ATSm5																								
ATSp1																								
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ATSp4																								
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FMF																								
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GRAV-2																								
GRAV-3																								
GRAVH-1																								

parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-1st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
GRAVH-2																								
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khs,sNH2																								
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khs,aaN																								
khs,ssnN																								
khs,aasN																								
khs,sOH																								
khs,dO																								
khs,ssO																								
khs,aaO																								
khs,sF																								
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MDEN-23																								
MDEN-33																								
MOMI-X																								
MOMI-Y																								

Figure S3. Heatmap of molecular descriptor weights representing their effect on the retention on BEH column determined by ANN. Blue – decreasing retention, red – increasing retention. M – MeOH as organic modifier, N – MeOH+10 mmol/L NH₃ as organic modifier, W- MeOH+2% H₂O as organic modifier.

parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
ALogP																								
ALogp2																								
AMR																								
BCUTw-1l																								
BCUTw-1h																								
BCUTc-1l																								
BCUTc-1h																								
BCUTp-1l																								
BCUTp-1h																								
PPSA-1																								
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FNSA-1																								
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WNSA-3																								
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RNCG																								
RPCS																								
RNCS																								
THSA																								
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RHSA																								
RPSA																								
fragC																								
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Wlambda3,unity																								
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parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
ATSm4																								
ATSm5																								
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tpsaEfficiency																								
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parameter	M-1st	M-1M	M-2M	M-3M	M-6M	M-9M	M-12M	M-reg	N-1st	N-1M	N-2M	N-3M	N-6M	N-9M	N-12M	N-reg	W-st	W-1M	W-2M	W-3M	W-6M	W-9M	W-12M	W-reg
GRAVH-2																								
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khs,ssssC																								
khs,sNH2																								
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khs,aaNH																								
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khs,aasN																								
khs,sOH																								
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MDEN-13																								
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MDEN-23																								
MDEN-33																								
MOMI-X																								
MOMI-Y																								

Figure S4. Heatmap of molecular descriptor weights representing their effect on the retention on diol column determined by ANN. Blue – decreasing retention, red – increasing retention. M – MeOH as organic modifier, N – MeOH+10 mmol/L NH₃ as organic modifier, W- MeOH+2% H₂O as organic modifier.

RPCG = the maximal positive charge (blue)/total positive charge (blue+black)

RHSA = sum of solvent accessible surface areas of atoms with absolute value of partial charges less than 0.2 (red) / total surface area (blue)

Figure S5. General illustration of molecules with high and low values of RPCG and RHSA.

RNCG = the maximal negative charge (blue)/total negative charge (blue+black)

RNCS = most negative surface area (red) * RNCG

Figure S6. General illustration of molecules with high and low values of RNCG and RNCS.

Figure S7. Retention times of selected acidic and alkaline compounds on silica, BEH, and diol column using MeOH as organic modifier. (A) t_R of analytes with pronounced acidic groups, (B) t_R of analytes with pronounced alkaline groups. 4.38 – 3-hydroxycinnamic acid, 4.57 – 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, 4.14 – flurbiprofen, 4.23 – ketoprofen, 4.31 – pravastatin, 4.48 – shikimic acid, 9.32 – darifenacin, 10.4 – desipramine, 9.54 – pindolol, 9.50 – propranolol, 7.15 – vardenafil.

Figure S8. (A) Histogram of standard deviations (SD) between weights of molecular descriptors calculated by ANN using the original and extended set of analytes measured on BEH column using MeOH as organic modifier. (B) Comparison of weights of molecular descriptors with the highest SD.

Figure S9. Principal Component Analysis of original set of 52 compounds (blue) and additional compounds eluting on silica and diol column (red).

Figure S10. Retention time of the 5 analytes with the highest values of FMF measured on silica column using MeOH (blue), MeOH+2% H_2O (yellow), and MeOH+10 mmol/L NH_3 (green).

Figure S11. Chemical structure of acebutolol with highlighted -NH- groups.

Figure S12. Percentage of analytes with increased (purple) and decreased (blue) retention times at selected data points when compared to the 1st injection on diol column using (A) MeOH, (B) MeOH + 2% H₂O, and (C) MeOH + 10 mmol/L NH₃ as organic modifier.

Figure S13. Comparison of weights of the molecular descriptors most affected over time on diol column. Weights determined by ANN based on analysis at 1st injection (dark blue), month 1 (light blue), month 2 (dark green), month 3 (light green), month 6 (dark yellow), month 9 (yellow), and month 12 (red).

Figure S14. Percentage of analytes with increased (purple) and decreased (blue) retention times at selected data points when compared to the 1st injection on BEH column using (A) MeOH, (B) MeOH + 2% H₂O, and (C) MeOH + 10 mmol/L NH₃ as organic modifier.

Figure S15. Weights of khs.sNH2 and MDEO-22 molecular descriptors determined by ANN based on the analyses on BEH column at the 1st injection (0M), after 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, and 12 months (M), and after regeneration (R).

Figure S16. Comparison of retention time shifts over time for alkaline and acidic compounds analyzed on a BEH column using MeOH as organic modifier.

Figure S17. Percentage of analytes with increased (purple) and decreased (blue) retention times at selected data points when compared to the 1st injection on silica column using (A) MeOH, (B) MeOH + 2% H₂O, and (C) MeOH + 10 mmol/L NH₃ as organic modifier.

Figure S18: Comparison of retention time shifts over time on silica column using (A) methanol, (B) MeOH+10 mmol/L NH₃, and (C) MeOH+ 2% H₂O as organic modifier.

Figure S19. Comparison of weights of the molecular descriptors most affected over time on silica column. Weights determined by ANN based on analysis at 1st injection (dark blue), month 1 (light blue), month 2 (dark green), month 3 (light green), month 6 (dark yellow), month 9 (yellow), and month 12 (red).

Figure S20: Comparison of % errors calculated between t_R after regeneration and t_R at the first injection on silica, BEH, and diol columns. %-error less than 0.5% (dark blue), 0.5 – 1.0% (light blue), 1.0 -2.0% (yellow), 2.0 -5.0% (pink), and over 5% (red).

Figure S21: Comparison of changes in retention time and peak width after regeneration procedure. k' closer to the value of the first injection after regeneration (blue) vs. after 12 months (red). Gray color represents k' within +/- 2%. (A) - silica column, (B) - BEH column, (C) - diol column.

References

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